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Phd Research and Study on Macro Economics by Iqbal Shaukat

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Abstract:

Economic development is very essential for every nation. In economics Development the economics education is very important, with the help of good economics policies we can achieve the goal of economics development. There are two parts of economics macro & micro. Economist studied all the aspects of economy. If you want the measure of economics Development you should analyze the main stream of economics. Micro economics we study the human behaviour. In the micro economics we study the price effect on demand and supply and method of return of output of production. In micro economics we analyze how the laws of utilities. In the micro economics we review of consumer behaviour. In the macro economics we study about the whole issues of economics which is relate to national level and international level. Economics study the regarding the different issue which is relate to consumer behaviour, national issues of entire nations. When we study and review of economics we can analyze whole country economics situation. {1-10}

Keywords: Macro Economics

Literature Review of Macro Economics

In the macro economics we study and measure of inflation rate. Inflation rate how the country reduce the purchasing power of people. We use the technique of index number, in the index number one year is base and the base year is compare with the current year, after this calculation we get actual rate of inflation. Statistics analyze the base year according to the wisdom and knowledge. After the one financial year the finance minister announces the federal budget, in which finance minister announces how to increase the receipts and control the expenditure. Finance ministry announced the new measure how the receipt will increase. The purpose of the budget proposal to create the economics prosperity. In budget different industries encourage through the tax holiday. In the federal budget taken measure how to create the tax culture in the country. In the macro economics we calculate the different method how to measure the gross domestic product. Gross domestic product meaning value of good and services produced in the country. The different method adopted how to measure the gross domestic product. Income method, expenditure method, production method. In the production we calculate the value of output good, which are manufacturer in the country. Income method in which we consider the people income salary or business profit and business income. In the expenditure method we calculate total expenditure on good and services. In macro economics we calculate the employment rate, the formula of employment rate total employed force divided by the total population. The basic purpose is that how employment and unemployment in the country. In the macro economics we calculate the total income. Gross domestic product divided by total population, with the help of this approach we calculate the total income of the country. Per capita income is the important part of macro economics. Per capita income can be calculated through the total income divided by the total population. Monetary policy is the important part of macro economics, in the monetary

policy central bank control the monetary extension by various tools.open market operations, maintain the reserve limit and cash reserves limit. In the open market operations in the case of inflation central bank sold the securities and bonds.as far as interest rate is concerned during the inflation central bank increase the interest rate,the impact of high interest rate the supply of money can be controlled. Maintenance the cash reserve limit is the important part of monetary policy.During the inflation central bank decrease the cash reserve limit of banks,the impact of cash reserve limit the supply of money is easily control..In the macro economics we study about the balance of payment.Balnce of payment capital Account, current Account, financial Accounts. In the current country exchange thd goods and services.capital Accounts country exchange Assest and securities as a exchange of remittance. If the inflow is higher than the out flow,than the capital accounts and currents and financial accounts is positive.Exchange rate is the important part of macro economics. Exchange rate means value of foreign currency against the local currency,there are two types of exchange rate.Fixed rates and floating rates.Fixed rate is issued by the central bank of the country.Floating rates changes by the market forces,for example due to imports of country the demand of foreign currency is higher than local currency,increase the demand in foreign currency the creat the devolution of local currency. In the macro economics we study about the devaluation of local currency.Devaluation of currency means revalue of currency according to the financial needs of country,for example we want increase of balance of payment we devalue our currency against the foreign currency,the basic purpose of devalue of currency discourage the imports.Balance of trade is the important part of macro economics.In the balance of trade we study difference between import and exports.if the imports is higher than the exports than balance of payment is negitive.if the export is higher than the imports the balance of payment is positive. In the macro economics we study the structure of duties and tariffs.in such cases we want discourage the imports government enforce duties and tariffs.in such cases when government encourage the any industry the duties and tariffs are reduced by the tax department.In the macro economics we study about the international agreement.in macro economics we study about the regiem of the agreements and what impacts on over trade and economy.In the macro economics we study about the role of IMF,world banks.. In the macro economics we study how these institute play the role in the country economy.In the macro economics we study about the impact of globalization on the economy.In the macro economics how the challanges of globalization can be faced.globalization interconnection of various around the world.In the macro economics we can study how we exchange the goods and services in the interconnection economy.Industrialization should be increase the country,the good and services should be increase.skill labour should be produced,the impact of skilled labours it will increase the good and services.Exchange rate should be maintained according to the financial needs of country.Exchand rate should be maintained and implemented.Monetary policy should be implemented according to financial needs of country.the basic purpose of monetary policy is lcontrol the inflation in the country.globalization challanges should be face according to the f needs of country.For the seck of globalization we should be aware from international markets.Devalue currency according to the financial needs and improve the balance of payment with rest of world.Balance of trade should be improved with other countries.For the macro economics stability duties and tariffs according to financial requirement of country.For the stability of macro economics economist should study international financial institutiones. of best macro economics model.{1-15}

Best Macro Economics Models Countries

Japan is the best model of macro economics,in japan create good out put.japan produced the skill labour,Japan achieved the highest growth in economy and produce the highest value of good and services and control the population.Germany is the good model of good macro economics model.Germany formed the good walfare system.Germany maintained the monetary system. Germany achieved the target regarding the production of good and services.In Germany many vocational institutes provide the traing to works.Australia,Canada is the model of macro economics,they provide the social facilities and flexible labour market.Australia,Canada maintain the monetary and fiscal polices very wall.China is the model of great economics model.China achieved the highest growth of economy in the recent years.Chinese built the capital projects like

dams.Chinesees faced the challanges of globalization with great spirit.In Bangladesh formed the good textile system.In Bangladesh training is provide to works for the better industrial result.{1-11}

Benefit of Macro Economics Qualifications

Economics qualifications is very important for every socitey.in the macro economics subject we study about the international trade.Balance of payment is studied in the macro economics.In the macro economics we study about the balance of trade.in macro economics we study about the economics of different countries.Monetry policy and fiscal policy is studied in the macro economics.In the macro economics we study about suchs countries which established the best macro economics stability.in the macro economics we study about the role of international financial institutiones like international monetary funds,world bank.In the macro economics we study about the how the exchange rate is maintained.In the macro economics we study about the taxation system of various policy.In the macro economics we study about the fiscal polices of different countries.In the macro economics we study about the capital market and stock of various countries.Macro economics provide the guideline how the effectiveness can be maintained of capital and stock market.Macro economics provide the guidance how the fiscal space between the expenditure and receipts can be filled.In macro economics we study about the inflation of various countries.Macro economics guide how the inflation can be measured.Macro economics provide the guidance how the inflation can be controlled.Macro economics provide the lession how to face the challanges of globalization.In the macro economics we study about the recession situations of the different economics.Macro economics provide the guidance about the duties and tariffs of various country.{1-20}

Connection between the Difference Subjects with Macro Economics

Various subject is interconnect with various subjects.Like financial management, managerial finance,Business finance,corporate finance.international economics,operation and production.In these subjects most topics relate to macro economics.For example in the operation and production management we study about of combination of Fectors of production,when we study the macro economics we study with the stance of Gross domestic product.For example in the financial management we study about the capital and stock market,this topic is relate to the macro economics.in the financial management about the international financial institutes,in the same manner in the macro economics we study about the financial institutes.In the financial management we study about the future value,present value,internal rate of return,in the same stance we study all aspects in the financial management.{1-20}

Research Regarding Macro Economics with Qualitative and Quantitative Perspective

I conducted the research regarding the importance of macro economics stability and importance of acro economics subjects importance.

I talked with different cetogeries regarding the importance of macro economics stability and importance of macro economics qualifications importance.

The results as fellow.

Table:

Cetogeries. Yes no.

Business. 2. 0

Student. 8. 2

Teacher.	10.	1
Economist.	4.	0
Tax consultant	8	0
Accountant.	5	0

All the audience agree about the macro economics stability is very important and macro economics qualifications is very important.

Conclusion

It to be concluded that the macro economics is very important for society.if one country maintain the macro economics stability they can achieve the goal of economics growth and development.Macro economics provide the guideline how to run the economics effectively.Macro economics provide the guideline how the stability come in the country. Macro economics professional can better implemented the macro economics polices,there fore in various countries the macro economics subject are included in syallbus of economics.There are the lot of connection between the financial management with other subjects like Financial management,Managerial economics, international economics.Macro economics provide the path how to control the monetary and fiscal space.Best implementation of macro economics can help the country to achieve the stable economics growth and development.

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